

SHAPE DISTORTION SIMULATIONS OF CARBON/EPOXY COMPOSITES USING A SIMPLIFIED MECHANICAL CONSTITUTIVE MODEL

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SUMMARY: During the last decade a lot of effort has been spent on development of tools for prediction of manufacturing induced residual stresses and shape distortions. The motivations for this are the high costs and lead-time associated with redesign and tool modifications that often are necessary before the specifications of high quality composite parts are met. The mechanical constitutive models used in these simulation tools ranges from linear or incremental elasticity to the most advanced and presumably most accurate models utilising thermo-chemo-rheologically complex viscoelasticity.

In a previous paper¹ the authors investigated the influence of the cure schedule on shape distortions of glass/epoxy angle brackets manufactured by resin transfer moulding (RTM). An important observation was that the spring-in did not change for a range of cure conditions and therefore we concluded that for cure conditions typical for RTM and autoclave consolidation of prepregs it may be possible to use a simpler mechanical constitutive relation than viscoelasticity. The constitutive model must however be able to treat both thermal effects and chemical shrinkage as well as frozen-in deformations caused by the mechanical boundary conditions during in-mould cure. Linear or incremental elastic models do not properly describe the frozen-in deformations and therefore a new, but relatively simple, mechanical constitutive relation was developed. The details of the model development and FE-implementation are described elsewhere².

In the present paper we use the new mechanical constitutive model in predictions of shape distortion for resin transfer moulded carbon fibre/high temperature epoxy U-beams and compare the predictions with experimental results. Of particular interest is the ability to predict the influence of fibre content and beam radius and therefore we study a through-thickness homogeneous fibre lay-up $[(0/90)_n]$ plain weave). The predictions are obtained by computer simulation of residual stress development during the two-step curing process (in-mould cure followed by a free-standing post cure) including mechanical interaction between tooling and composite. The properties of the curing composite material are calculated from resin and fibre properties using micro-mechanics. Predicted spring-in is compared to measured values for two beam radii and two fibre contents. In the computer simulations the mechanical interaction with the tooling results in a small difference in spring-in between the small and large radius U-beams after demoulding. Increasing the fibre volume content from 46% to 52% leads to a decrease of the predicted spring-in angle of 0.1°. The overall agreement between predicted and experimentally determined spring-in is good which support the validity of the simulation approach and mechanical constitutive relation. The results also show the importance of using appropriate mechanical boundary conditions during cure and residual stress/shape distortion simulations.

KEYWORDS: shape distortion, resin transfer moulding, epoxy, carbon fibre, process simulation

INTRODUCTION

Composite structures used in aerospace applications are often manufactured by autoclave moulding of unidirectional prepreg tapes. Although this route leads to good control of the fibre orientations and good mechanical properties, the costs are considerable. In the 1990's resin transfer moulding (RTM) became established as an alternative process for manufacturing of aerospace components with benefits like reduced layup times and potential for high dimensional tolerances by the use of two-sided tools. An important aspect is then the ability to predict and compensate the tooling for shape distortions that occur during manufacturing. A significant part of the shape distortions is due to thermally induced shrinkage during cool-down from the curing temperature but also chemical shrinkage of the polymeric matrix during cure cause a similar shape distortion. For channel and angle components the distortion in shape will be manifested by a change in angle as shown in Figure 1, the phenomenon is often termed as spring-in.

Fig. 1 Thermally distorted angle section

For an unconstrained single curved angle section the deformation due to a uniform temperature change is due to expansional strains. Radford³ showed that the spring-in angle $\Delta\theta$ of a section with initial angle θ and with homogeneous material properties is,

$$\Delta\theta = \frac{\theta (\alpha_{\theta} - \alpha_r) \Delta T}{1 + \alpha_r \Delta T} \approx \theta (\alpha_{\theta} - \alpha_r) \Delta T \quad \text{Eqn. 1}$$

where α_{θ} and α_r are the coefficients of thermal expansion in the tangential and through-thickness directions respectively and ΔT is the temperature change. Expansional strains due to moisture and chemical shrinkage can be accounted for in an analogous manner³.

To predict manufacturing induced shape distortions of parts with complex geometry at mechanically constrained and possibly non-isothermal cure conditions a process simulation tool is required. During the last decade a lot of effort has been spent on development of tools for prediction of manufacturing induced residual stresses and shape distortions. The motivations for this are the high costs and lead-time associated with redesign and tool modifications that often are necessary before the specifications of high quality composite parts are met. The mechanical constitutive models used in these simulation tools ranges from linear or incremental elasticity⁴ to the most advanced and presumably most accurate, but also more complex to use, models utilising thermo-chemo-rheologically complex viscoelasticity⁵.

In RTM a two-step cure schedule is often employed, first an in-mould cure and then a free-standing post-cure after demoulding of the component. Experimental investigation of the influence of variations in the cure schedule on shape distortions of glass/epoxy angle brackets manufactured by RTM was the subject of a previous paper¹ by the authors. An important observation was that the spring-in did not change for a range of cure conditions and therefore we concluded that for cure conditions typical for RTM and autoclave consolidation of prepregs it may be possible to use a simpler mechanical constitutive relation than viscoelasticity. The constitutive model must however be able to treat thermal effects, chemical shrinkage as well as frozen-in deformations generated at the rubber-glass transition during constrained cure. Linear or incremental elastic models do not properly describe the frozen-in deformations and therefore a new, but still simple, mechanical constitutive relation was developed. As a continuation of this work a thermo-mechanical process model, including the new mechanical constitutive relation, for prediction of residual stress development and shape distortions was described and implemented in a general purpose FE-program^{2,6}. The process model has then successfully been used to predict spring-in of two-step cured thin and thick angle sections of glass fibre weave/room temperature curing epoxy^{2,7,8} and shape distortions of a complex shaped one-step cured aerospace component of carbon fibre weave/high temperature epoxy².

The objective of the present paper is to check the validity of the simulation approach for a two-step cured carbon fibre/high temperature epoxy system. The new mechanical constitutive model is used in numerical predictions of spring-in for resin transfer moulded U-beams and the predictions are compared with experimental results. In the simulations three different mechanical boundary conditions are evaluated to assess the effect of the interaction between tooling and composite during in-mould cure.

MATERIALS AND MATERIAL PROPERTIES

The reinforcement used for the experiments is a thermo formable, 193 g/m², plain carbon fibre weave with a $\pm 45^\circ$ arrangement. The resin is an aerospace grade high temperature epoxy. The properties of neat resin and fibres are listed in Table 1 respectively Table 2. Based on these data the effective properties of a $\pm 45^\circ$ plain weave were predicted using self-consistent field micromechanics⁹ and 3-D laminate theory¹⁰ for two fibre contents, see Table 3. Crimp in the weave was accounted for by reduction of the longitudinal fibre stiffness with a knock-down factor.

Table 1 Neat resin properties

Property	Source	Value
Young's modulus in glassy state (GPa)	[11]	3.3
Poisson's ratio in glassy state	Assumed	0.35
Shear modulus of fully cured material in rubbery state (GPa)	Estimated	0.012
In-mould cure temperature (°C)	[11]	160
Glass transition temperature after in-mould cure (°C)	*	188
Degree of cure at vitrification during in-mould cure	[12]	0.85
Degree of cure after in-mould cure	[11]	0.91
Free-standing post cure temperature (°C)	[11]	180
Glass transition temperature after post cure (°C)	*	201
Degree of cure after post cure	[11]	0.94
Instantaneous coefficient of thermal expansion in glassy state (10 ⁻⁶ /°C)	†	54+0.16T
Coefficient of thermal expansion in rubbery state (1/°C)	†	136·10 ⁻⁶
Total chemical shrinkage after post cure	[12]	-0.049

*: Determined by DSC at a scanning rate of 20°C/min.

†: Measured by the Swedish National Testing and Research Institute by TMA analysis.

EXPERIMENTAL

In a previous study, a number of U-beams were manufactured in a steel tool by RTM to investigate the effect from variations in the process conditions on the mechanical properties of the beams¹³. The U-beams were 400 mm long with 35 mm web, 65 mm flanges and 4 mm wall thickness. Beam radius, fibre content, preforming method and vacuum assistance were varied according to a factorial design. After mould closure, the mould was heated to 120°C in a hot air oven. The epoxy was preheated to 80°C prior to injection with 1 bar pressure and vacuum assistance according to the experimental plan. After complete mould filling, the tool was placed in a hot air oven at 160°C for in-mould cure for at least 3 hours. The long curing time was necessary to heat the tool sufficiently. A steel tool with at least 25 mm wall thickness was used.

Table 2 Fibre properties of HTA fibres (PAN precursor).

Property	Value	Source
Axial Young's modulus (GPa)	238	[14]
Crimp knock down factor	0.83	*
Transverse Young's modulus (GPa)	40	[15]
In plane shear modulus (GPa)	22	*
Major Poisson's ratio	0.20	[16]
Transverse Poisson's ratio	0.25	*
Axial coefficient of thermal expansion (1/°C)	-0.1·10 ⁻⁶	[14]
Transverse coefficient of thermal expansion (1/°C)	10·10 ⁻⁶	[15]

*: Back calculated from laminate properties of tested GB200/RTM6 laminates.

Table 3 Calculated [±45°]_n laminate data.

Laminate [±45°] _n properties	Glassy state		Rubbery state	
	V _f =46%	V _f =52%	V _f =46%	V _f =52%
In plane Young's modulus (GPa)	11	12	0.13	0.15
In plane Poisson's ratio	0.80	0.80	0.997	0.997
In plane shear modulus (GPa)	24	27	23	25
Through thickness Young's modulus (GPa)	9.2	10.0	3.0	3.3
Out of plane Poisson's ratio	0.09	0.09	0.002	0.002
Out of plane shear modulus (GPa)	2.7	3.1	0.03	0.04
In plane coefficient of thermal expansion (10 ⁻⁶ /°C)	6.2	5.5	-	-
Out of plane coefficient of thermal expansion (10 ⁻⁶ /°C)	76	69	-	-
In plane coefficient of curing expansion	0.03	0.02	0.00	0.05
Out of plane coefficient of curing expansion	0.33	0.30	0.53	0.48

The in-mould cure was followed by cool-down to room temperature, demoulding and a free-standing post-cure at 180°C for 2 hours. According to the data in Table 1, vitrification occurs during in-mould cure at a degree of cure of 85%. After in-mould cure the glass transition temperature as determined by DSC is 188°C. Since the post cure temperature is lower than that the whole post-cure cycle is performed in the glassy state.

A total number of 14 U-beams were manufactured. Inner beam radius (R_i), fibre content (V_f) and measured

average void content in the radii (V_v) are presented in Table 4. After manufacturing, the dimensions of each beam were carefully determined according to Fig. 2 by a measuring machine with a precision of $\pm 1\mu\text{m}$. The distances l_1 and l_2 are measured at three locations along the beam. The male tool has a draft angle of 1.40° . The spring-in angle is then determined by,

Fig. 2 Spring-in measurement

$$\Delta\bar{\theta} = 1.40^\circ - \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\bar{l}_1 - \bar{l}_2}{2 \cdot 30} \right) \quad \text{Eqn. 2}$$

The experimentally determined spring-in angles ($\Delta\theta$) are presented in Table 4.

Table 4 Beam radii, fibre contents, measured void contents and measured spring-in angles.

Beam no.	R_i (mm)	V_f (%)	V_v (%)	Average ($^\circ$)	
2	0.8	46	-	1.07	1.14
5	0.8	46	-	1.21	
6	0.8	52	-	0.91	1.06
11	0.8	52	0.6	1.20	
4	0.8	52	0.8	1.04	
10	0.8	52	1.7	1.10	
1	5.0	46	0.4	1.13	1.08
8	5.0	46	1.2	1.03	
14	5.0	52	-	1.11	1.09
12	5.0	52	<0.1	1.12	
13	5.0	52	<0.1	1.11	
7	5.0	52	0.7	1.08	
9	5.0	52	0.8	1.10	
3	5.0	52	1.0	1.04	

ANALYSIS

Mechanical constitutive model

The “simplified” mechanical constitutive relation used in this paper can be derived from linear visco-elasticity^{2,6} but may also be viewed as a linear elastic relation with temperature or phase dependent material properties and an unstressed reference or equilibrium configuration defined in the rubbery state ($T \geq T_g$ where T_g is the glass transition temperature). The stress-strain relation is expressed as,

$$\sigma_i = \begin{cases} C_{ij}^r (\varepsilon_j - \varepsilon_j^E) & , T \geq T_g (X) \\ C_{ij}^g (\varepsilon_j - \varepsilon_j^E) - (C_{ij}^g - C_{ij}^r) (\varepsilon_j - \varepsilon_j^E) \Big|_{t=t_{vit}} & , T < T_g (X) \end{cases} \quad \text{Eqn. 3}$$

where σ_i and ε_j are the stress respectively total strain vectors in contracted Voigt notation. t_{vit} denote the time for the last rubber-glass transition. C_{ij} is the stiffness matrix for which superscripts g and r denote properties in glassy respectively rubbery state. The free expansion ε_j^E is a function of temperature, T , and degree of cure, X . By assuming that it can be decomposed into two independent terms the free expansion is expressed as,

$$\varepsilon_j^E = \varepsilon_j^T + \varepsilon_j^C \quad \text{Eqn. 4}$$

where ε_j^T is thermal expansion and $-\varepsilon_j^C$ shrinkage due to chemical reactions. The thermal expansion and chemical shrinkage terms are defined as,

$$\varepsilon_j^T = \int_0^t \alpha_j (T, X) \frac{dT}{dt'} dt', \quad \text{where } \alpha_j (T, X) = \begin{cases} \alpha_j^l & , X < X_{gel} \text{ and } T \geq T_g (X) \\ \alpha_j^r & , X \geq X_{gel} \text{ and } T \geq T_g (X) \\ \alpha_j^g & , T < T_g (X) \end{cases} \quad \text{Eqn. 5}$$

$$\varepsilon_j^C = \int_0^t \beta_j (T, X) \frac{dX}{dt'} dt', \quad \text{where } \beta_j (T, X) = \begin{cases} \beta_j^l & , X < X_{gel} \text{ and } T \geq T_g (X) \\ \beta_j^r & , X \geq X_{gel} \text{ and } T \geq T_g (X) \\ \beta_j^g & , T < T_g (X) \end{cases} \quad \text{Eqn. 6}$$

where α_j is the coefficient of thermal expansion and β_j the coefficient of “curing expansion”. Superscripts l , r and g indicate properties in the liquid, rubbery and glassy state respectively for the temperature (or phase) dependent properties.

Experimental determination of all material parameters in Equations 3-6 for an orthotropic laminate is an extensive task. A more economical approach, which is used here, is to determine the fibre and neat resin properties and based on those calculate the homogenised laminate properties for the glassy and rubbery state by micromechanics and 3-dimensional laminate theory as presented in a previous section.

The mechanical constitutive model, including the free expansion terms, has been incrementalised and implemented in the general purpose FE-code ANSYS using the user programmable feature USERMAT. A detailed description of a similar implementation into the FE-program ABAQUS is presented elsewhere^{2,6}.

Simulation strategy

In general a process simulation with the purpose to predict shape distortions would involve a coupled thermal and mechanical analysis. For the present case, where we have a relatively thin part with high fibre loading and long cure times, we do not expect any significant exothermal temperature peaks to develop during cure. Therefore we assume that the temperature in the part is spatially uniform and equal to the tool temperature. Due to the long cure times we may also de-couple chemical shrinkage and thermal contraction/expansion into separate events, i.e. the degree of cure evolve at isothermal conditions at the cure temperature (and post-cure temperature) and the cooling after complete cure occurs without further chemical reactions. Since the post-cure is made free-standing it is also reasonable to assume that the heating is sufficiently fast to neglect any increase of the degree of cure during the heating to the post-cure temperature. With these assumptions/simplifications we do not need to perform a thermal simulation, the relevant information on how the state variables temperature and degree of cure evolve during different process steps is directly given by the information in Table 1. For the present case we therefore only perform a mechanical simulation in eight load steps, with temperature and degree of cure prescribed according to Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 Cure schedule and degree of cure evolution used in simulation

FE-analysis

A 2-D FE-model of the U-beam was created in ANSYS 6.1 using first order generalised plane strain elements (PLANE182). Three different mechanical boundary conditions were evaluated for the simulation of residual stress development during in-mould cure:

- 1) Free-standing, only rigid body motion constrained (corresponds with a linear elastic material model to Equation 1).
- 2) Frictionless contact, realised by use of contact elements.
- 3) Perfect bonding between tool surface and surface of composite part, realised by imposing the condition $u_i = x_i \cdot \alpha_{tool} (T - T_{ref})$ on all exterior nodes of the composite part. u_i , x_i and α_{tool} are displacement vector, position vector respectively thermal expansion coefficient of the tool. T_{ref} is a

reference temperature defined to be equal to room temperature.

The FE-model for the contact boundary condition that contains both the U-beam and the stiff tool is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 FE-model

The simulation of the demoulding step is made different for the three types of in-mould cure boundary conditions. For the free-standing case, demoulding is not an issue. For the contact condition demoulding is simulated by “removing” the elements that define the tool by using the ANSYS element death option. Finally, for the bonded case demoulding is simulated by removing all mechanical boundary conditions except those required to prevent rigid body motion. All simulations of post-cure were made with boundary conditions that represent free-standing conditions.

Spring-in predictions, based on the three different types of boundary conditions described above, are presented in Table 5 for the two beam radii and fibre contents that were characterised experimentally, c.f. Table 4.

Table 5. Predicted spring-in and its components

R_i (mm)	Boundary condition	Spring-in after demoulding		Spring-in after post cure	
		V_f 46%	V_f 52%	V_f 46%	V_f 52%
0.8	Free-standing	1.60°	1.45°	1.64°	1.49°
0.8	Contact elements	1.33°	1.21°	1.37°	1.26°
0.8	Bonded to tool	1.23°	1.12°	1.27°	1.16°
5.0	Free-standing	1.60°	1.45°	1.64°	1.49°
5.0	Contact elements	1.24°	1.13°	1.28°	1.17°
5.0	Bonded to tool	1.19°	1.09°	1.24°	1.13°

DISCUSSION

The simulation results presented in Table 5 show that we get very different spring-in predictions when different mechanical boundary conditions during in-mould cure are used. For the smaller radius and 52% fibre content the predicted spring-in after demoulding become 1.12° if the U-beam is modeled as bonded to the tool surface during the entire in-mould cure. When the

interaction with the tooling instead is modeled as frictionless contact (zero adhesion between tool and composite) the predicted spring-in increases by 0.09° to 1.21° . If the mechanical interaction with the tooling is completely ignored (free-standing conditions) the predicted spring-in become very high, 1.45° . The same trend is observed for the larger radius. The fact that the mechanical interaction between the tooling and composite has a great influence on the resulting spring-in has also been observed numerically and experimentally by others¹⁷. In Fig. 5 the predicted through-thickness residual stress after cool-down but before demoulding is presented for the bonded and contact conditions. For the bonded condition the residual through-thickness tensile stress is predicted to be up to 227 MPa, which means that the part will fail by delaminations before demoulding if the part remain bonded to the tool surfaces during the entire in-mould cure and the following cool-down to room temperature that precedes demoulding. When contact conditions are used on the other hand through-thickness contraction, due to chemical shrinkage and thermal contraction, give the part some free-space to move inside the mould cavity and this leads to a significant reduction of the residual through-thickness tensile stress, 10 MPa instead of 227 MPa. Inspections of polished cross-sections of as manufactured 0.8 mm U-beams showed no signs of delaminations and hence it is clear that, for the present case, the bonded boundary condition is not valid for the entire in-mould cure cycle including the cool-down to room temperature. It is however possible that the part remains bonded to the tool until after vitrification and releases from the tool during the last part of the cure process or during cool-down. For this case the bonded condition will give an accurate prediction of the spring-in after demoulding since the stress state at vitrification is properly modelled, c.f. Equation 3. With the friction free contact boundary condition on the other hand, the deformation of the part is limited to be within the stiff mould cavity but the part may release from or slide against the tool surface and this is the least constraint that may be on the part before demoulding. From this discussion we conclude that we would expect the experimentally determined spring-in to be between the predictions based on bonded and contact conditions.

A comparison between the predictions presented in Table 5 and the experimentally determined spring-in, Table 4, after post cure shows that we have slightly overestimated the spring-in. Using “bonded” boundary conditions we predict 1.27° and 1.16° for U-beams with 0.8 mm radius at 46% respectively 52% fibre content as compared to the experimental averages 1.11° and 1.08° . The increase in fibre content from 46% to 52% is predicted to decrease the spring-in by 0.1° which is less than the experimental scatter. For the 5.0 mm radius U-beams the predicted spring-in is 1.24° and 1.13° as compared to the experimental averages 1.08° and 1.09° . To summarise the spring-in is over estimated by approximately 0.1° when the U-beam is modelled as bonded to the tool surface. When contact boundary conditions are used the spring-in is overestimated even more and the free-standing condition that neglects any interaction between composite and tooling give a very high estimate of the spring-in.

According Equation 1, the radius is not expected to affect the spring-in angle for an unconstrained part. However, the simulation results show that for U-beams that are mechanically constrained by the mould during cure the spring-in should increase slightly when the radius become very small. The measured spring-in angles for the small (0.8 mm) and large (5.0 mm) radius U-beams do not differ but the predicted difference is small compared to the present experimental scatter.

The used mechanical constitutive relation imply that part of the chemical shrinkage strains that develop during in-mould cure is counterbalanced by frozen-in strains at the phase transition from rubbery to glassy state. The frozen-in strains may be more or less recoverable by a secondary heating of the material to the rubbery state (totally recoverable according to Equation 3), e.g. during post cure at sufficiently high temperature. This might give a large

increase in spring-in during post cure if the post cure temperature is higher than the glass transition temperature obtained after in-mould cure. In the present case the whole post-cure step is performed in the glassy state and from Table 5 we can see that the spring-in angle is predicted to increase by 0.04° during post-cure. Actual measurement of the spring-in angle on a beam (beam 14 in Table 4) before and after post-cure gave the result 1.03° and 1.11° respectively, an increase of 0.08° compared to the predicted 0.04° . Apparently some of the frozen-in deformation is recovered during post-cure even if the material never enters the rubbery state.

Fig. 5 Predicted residual stress level before demoulding for the U-beam with small radius and 52% fibre content. a) Composite bonded to tools surface, b) Contact conditions (tool shaded in gray and magnified displacements).

CONCLUSIONS

Spring-in was predicted from fibre and neat resin properties using a simple constitutive relation for a curing resin that incorporates the effects of chemical shrinkage and the phase transition at T_g . Micromechanics and 3-dimensional laminate theory were used to calculate homogenized laminate properties. These data were then used in FE-simulations to predict the spring-in of U-beams before and after post-cure. Predicted spring-in is compared to measured values for two beam radii and two fibre contents. In the computer simulations the mechanical interaction with the tooling results in a small difference in spring-in between the small and large radius U-beams after demoulding. Increasing the fibre volume content from 46% to 52% leads to a decrease of the predicted spring-in angle of 0.1° . The overall agreement between predicted and experimentally determined spring-in is good which support the validity of the simulation approach and mechanical constitutive relation. The results also show the importance of using appropriate mechanical boundary conditions during cure and residual stress/shape distortion simulations.

REFERENCES

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- ¹ Svanberg JM, Holmberg JA. An experimental investigation on mechanisms for manufacturing induced shape distortions in homogeneous and balanced laminates. *Composites Part A* 2001;32(6):827-838.
 - ² Svanberg JM. Predictions of manufacturing induced shape distortions – high performance thermoset composites. Doctoral Thesis, Luleå University of Technology, Report 2002:40, 2002.
 - ³ Radford DW, Diefendorf RJ. Shape instabilities in composites resulting from laminate anisotropy. *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites* 1993;12:58-75.
 - ⁴ Johnston A, Vaziri R, Pourtarsip A. A Plane Strain Model for Process-Induced Deformation of Laminated Composite Structures. *Journal of Composite Materials* 2001;35(16):1435-1469.
 - ⁵ White SR, Kim KK. Process-induced residual stress analysis of AS4/3501-6 composite material. *Mechanics of Composite Materials and Structures* 1998;5:153-186.
 - ⁶ Svanberg JM, Holmberg JA. Prediction of shape distortions, Part I. FE-implementation of a path dependent constitutive model. Submitted *Composites Part A* 2002.
 - ⁷ Svanberg JM, Holmberg JA. Prediction of shape distortions, Part II. Experimental validation and analysis of boundary conditions. Submitted *Composites Part A* 2002.
 - ⁸ Svanberg JM. Shape distortion of non-isothermally cured composite angle bracket. *Plastics, Rubber and Composites* 2002;31(9):398-404.
 - ⁹ McCullough RL. Micro-models for composite materials - continuous fiber composites. In: *Delaware Composites Design Encyclopedia - Volume 2: Micromechanical Materials Modelling* (Eds. Carlsson LA, Gillespie JW). Technomic Publishing Co., Inc., Lancaster and Basel, 1990.
 - ¹⁰ Gudmundsson P, and Zang W. An analytic model for thermoelastic properties of composite laminates containing transverse matrix cracks. *International Journal of Solids and Structures* 1993;30:3211-3231.
 - ¹¹ RTM6: 180°C Epoxy system for R.T.M. (Resin Transfer Moulding): Monocomponent System. Product data sheet N0 000621, Brochier, PO Box 272, 33 ave. Franklin Roosevelt, F-69152 Décines-Charpieu Cedex, France, 1994.
 - ¹² Holmberg JA. Resin transfer moulded composite materials: processing-structure-property relationships. Doctoral Thesis, Luleå University of Technology, Report 1997:10, 1997.
 - ¹³ Holmberg JA, Berglund LA. Manufacturing and performance of RTM U-beams. *Composites Part A* 1997;28(6):513-521.
 - ¹⁴ Tenax[®], The carbon fibre for high performance composites. Datasheet from Enka, Enka, 1986.
 - ¹⁵ Diefendorf RJ. Carbon/graphite fibres. In: *Engineered Materials Handbook: Volume 1: Composites*. ASM International, USA, 1987, pp. 49-53.
 - ¹⁶ Mallick PK. *Fiber-reinforced composites: materials, manufacturing and design*. Marcel Dekker, New York, 1988.
 - ¹⁷ Fernlund G, Rahman N, Courdji R, Bresslauer R, Poursartip A, Willden K, Nelson K. Experimental and numerical study of the effect of cure cycle, tool surface, geometry, and lay-up on the dimensional fidelity of autoclave-processed composite parts. *Composites Part A* 2002;33:341-351.